

EDUCATIONAL METHODS FOR BILINGUAL KIDS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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The process of formation of the personality of a literate child is carried out through the assimilation of the socio-historical experience of humanity in the conditions of upbringing and education. This happens in a variety of activities. As a result, the educated child enters the system of social relations of the society in which he lives. A literate child's experience of acquiring social experience is a long and complex process. The difficulty lies in the fact that, on the one hand, an intelligent child has to master the human experience, which is complex in terms of content, volume and level of generalization, and on the other hand, he has not yet mastered the methods of mastering this experience.

In the process of upbringing and education, an adult chooses the content that is understandable to a knowledgeable child, guides his learning. The leading role of education in the development of the personality of a literate child is determined by this. It takes into account the mental and physiological capabilities of the child, their enthusiasm. It takes into account the mental and physiological capabilities of the child, their enthusiasm. In this regard, the educational process itself does not remain constant. It changes: its content becomes richer and more complex, its forms change, the ways of influencing the personality of a growing person become more and more diverse.

Education is one of the external factors affecting human development. Education is carried out under the guidance of an educator in order to develop positive qualities in a person systematically with specific goals in mind. But the strength of the influence of upbringing and its result are determined by the cooperation of factors such as heredity and environment. Under the influence of upbringing, qualities that could not be given by the environment are acquired, that is, knowledge, information is acquired.

1. Thanks to education, birth defects can be changed and a person can be matured. For example, the blind and deaf are also educated and prepared for life along with healthy people.

2. The negative influence of the environment can be eliminated with the help of education.

3. Education always sets a goal for the future.

The change in education is related to the "closest development zones" of the child, which are characterized by the emergence of psychological and physiological opportunities to acquire knowledge, skills, activities, etc., of a more complex content (for example, walking after crawling; mastering active speech after crawling; mastering knowledge at the level of concepts after having a considerable amount of imagination; the emergence of object-based play, work activities, etc.). Education and training based on the "zone of proximal development" go ahead of today's level of development and advance the development of the intelligent child.

The development of human personality goes through several stages. Each successive stage is strongly related to the previous one, the previously achieved stage is higher, it is integrated into the structure of the stage. The development formed at the early age stage is not temporary, but permanent for a person. The connection of content, methods, forms of organization is a characteristic feature of education from the first stage to the end.

The decisive role of education in the development of the personality of a literate child is especially clearly manifested in public institutions for blind and deaf literate children. The education system developed for such intelligent children ensures their preparation for marriage and work.

However, education that does not accelerate the development of a child should not artificially accelerate the mental development of any aspect of it. Therefore, in the pedagogy of preschool education, the purpose of comprehensive and harmonious development of the personality of the intelligent child, enrichment of his development is set [2. 1,3].

The leadership role of education in the development of the personality of a literate child determines the leadership role of the pedagogue, his responsibility for the formation of the personality of every literate child.

Education and development of a literate child the role of activity. The activity of a literate child helps to master the socio-historical experience, on the basis of which his role is formed in various types of activities such as knowledge, demonstration, play, the simplest work and study, as well as behavior. A knowledgeable child shows activity by mastering one or another activity, and at the same time acquires knowledge, skills, and abilities related to this activity. On this basis, various abilities and personality traits are formed in him.

The active position of the literate child in the activity made him not only an object of education, but also a subject of education. This knowledge determines the leadership role of activities in the education and development of the child. During the age-related periods of the development and upbringing of literate children, different types of activities coexist and interact, but their role is not the same: at each stage, a leading type of activity is distinguished, in which the main achievements in the development of a literate child are manifested. Each activity is characterized by a need, reasons, purpose of activity, topic, actions performed with means, objects and, finally, a result. Scientific data shows that the intelligent child acquires them not immediately, but gradually and under the guidance of an adult. Diversity and richness of the activities of a literate child, success in mastering it depends on upbringing and educational conditions in the family, literate kindergarten. From the early years of a literate child, the simplest types of activities are the basis for the formation of his personal abilities, characteristics and attitude to the surrounding things.

According to scientific studies, the social and cognitive activity of a literate child of preschool age develops in the play activity that becomes the leader in the preschool age. During the games under the guidance of educators, intelligent children acquire knowledge about various methods of movement, objects, their properties and signs. Knowledgeable children understand space and time relations, relationships of similarity and sameness, acquire concepts. Action games help to develop movements, to find direction in space. In joint games, intelligent children understand and master the importance of relationships between people, coordination of actions, expand their imagination about the surrounding things [3. 3].

The teacher achieves the expected results only when he awakens a strong need for activity in the student and helps him to form new character traits.

Age characteristics of intelligent children of preschool age and educate them. Based on the rule about the leadership role of activities in raising and developing a literate child, it is necessary to organize his life in educational institutions and in the family so that he is rich in various types of activities. They should be provided with guidance aimed at enriching content, mastering new skills, and developing independence.

The content, means, and methods of upbringing and education are explained by the development process of children and their age. In particular, when working with young educated children, it is taken into account that they are not completely adapted to independent life.

In the next age groups, the independence and adaptability of the literate preschool child increases significantly, accordingly, the tasks, content, tools and methods of educational work change. The level of development reached by the end of preschool age of a bilingual child makes it possible to complicate the educational work carried out with them. Classification of the content and methods of educational tasks according to age is based on the division of human life into periods accepted in modern science. On the one hand, the fact that time cannot be turned back, how long a person's life lasts, and on the other hand, the progress of mental development explained by the upbringing and education system are the basis of age differentiation. Age periods are mandatory stages of human development [2. 4].

At an early age, children master various movements such as crawling, crawling, hanging on something, and walking. The timing and sequence of some types of movement depends on the specific characteristics of children and the educational system. Already, due to good feeding, care, and frequent communication with children, they start to walk independently much earlier than when these conditions were not present. Sensory development, fundamentals of mental development, improvement of feelings, perception, and imagination are of great importance in the early years.

The formation of speech is an important age characteristic of literate children up to 3 years old. By the age of 3, literate children have mastered almost all aspects of their mother tongue and use speech as a means of communication with adults and peers.

The system of raising educated children of the first age is a component of the general education and training of the young generation.

In preschool age, the development of the child's body continues: from 3 to 5 years old, the growth rate of the child slows down a bit compared to the previous age, but it increases again from 5 to 8 years old. Along with the general growth and increase in body weight, anatomical changes and functional development of all the main tissues and organs of the child occur. Gradually, the skeleton hardens, the size of muscles increases, and the ability of the child's body to work increases. At the same time, nerve cells quickly get tired and the brain dries up. By the age of 6-7, a child can successfully master complex movements such as walking, running, jumping, hanging on a rope, throwing, and even skiing and skating.

Physical education plays a central role in working with children of preschool age. In accordance with the capabilities of an intelligent child, a system of using specific means and methods of influence in the family and in an intelligent kindergarten: life, diet, gymnastic exercises and active games, training methods are determined. The functional activity of the cerebral cortex improves in an intelligent child of preschool age. The high level of sensitivity of the nervous system determines the sharpness and sharpness of perception, the impressionability of intelligent children, therefore, the selection of impressions and knowledge (which is mainly the simplest knowledge about the surrounding life) is of great importance in raising and educating a preschool-aged intelligent child.

However, if the child's natural curiosity is not satisfied, he becomes passive. For example, intelligent children of middle age are manifested in various types of activity, novelty and sharpness of perception are characteristic. Under the influence of adults, the activities of preschool children

become voluntary, which is extremely important for training attentiveness during educational activities.

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